

Sherpa's idea project

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Abstract- Members of the Nepalese ethnic group known as Sherpas live in the high peaks of the Himalayas and are renowned for setting speed climbing records. Sherpas are extraordinary individuals. Their superpowers are based on the fact that they may be better at harnessing oxygen than the rest of us. The endocrine system plays an important role in improving the ability of blood hemoglobin to carry oxygen and therefore accelerating the burning of the energy source that the body requires. Exploiting the phenomenon considers a target to solve the issue of blood diseases.

Index Terms- cellular respiration, Sherpa, erythropoietin, Hemoglobin

I. INTRODUCTION

The world suffers from the spreading of diseases either infectious and non-infectious diseases. One of the most rigid rapidly spreading disease is blood diseases, such as sickle cell disease and raising of blood pressure and so on, which plagued about 25% of the total patients in the entire world. These diseases are synthesized relying on:

1. Understanding disease mechanisms: By synthesizing blood diseases, scientists can study the underlying mechanisms that lead to the development and progression of these conditions. This knowledge can help in identifying potential targets for treatment and developing new therapeutic approaches.
2. Drug discovery and development: Synthesizing blood diseases allows researchers to test the efficacy of various drugs and treatments in a controlled environment. This process helps in identifying potential drug candidates that can effectively treat or manage these diseases.

III. WRITE DOWN YOUR STUDIES AND FINDINGS

A. Structure of the erythropoietin, and how synthesizing it can be possible

Erythropoietin (EPO) is a glycoprotein hormone that plays a crucial role in the production of red blood cells. It is primarily produced by the kidneys, although a small amount is also synthesized in the liver. EPO stimulates the bone marrow to produce more red blood cells, which are responsible for carrying oxygen throughout the body. The structure of erythropoietin consists of a single polypeptide chain of about 165-166 amino acids, with a molecular weight of approximately 30,000 Daltons. It contains four alpha-helical bundles known as helices A, B, C, and D. The protein also has three disulfide bridges that help stabilize its structure.

3. Personalized medicine: Blood diseases often have different subtypes or variations, which may require personalized treatment approaches. Synthesizing these diseases helps in studying their specific characteristics, enabling the development of personalized treatment strategies tailored to individual patients.
4. Testing diagnostic tools: Synthesizing blood diseases provides an opportunity to evaluate and improve diagnostic tools used for early detection and monitoring of these conditions. This includes developing more accurate laboratory tests, imaging techniques, or biomarkers that can aid in diagnosis and disease monitoring.
5. Education and training: Synthesizing blood diseases allows medical students, researchers, and healthcare professionals to gain hands-on experience with these conditions in a controlled setting. This practical training enhances their understanding of disease pathology, diagnosis, and treatment options.
6. Ethical considerations: In some cases, synthesizing blood diseases may be preferred over using animal models or human subjects for research purposes due to ethical concerns or limitations associated with those methods.

II. IDENTIFY, RESEARCH AND COLLECT IDEA

Energy source for all living organisms is the food, and food distributes into nutritional components, like carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, minerals, etc. The depolymerization of the previous components yields the desired energy for the body like in the cellular respiration. Hemoglobin, transportation of the oxygen through the blood, is a transfer protein and crucial to the depolymerization process that occurs in the digestion of the food. So, from the findings the project will depend on extracting the responsible hormone (EP) to use it in help blood patients.

Synthesizing erythropoietin can be achieved through recombinant DNA technology. Here is a general overview of the process:

1. Identification and isolation: The gene encoding erythropoietin is identified and isolated from human or animal sources that naturally produce it.
2. Gene cloning: The isolated gene is then inserted into a suitable expression vector (such as a plasmid) using restriction enzymes and ligases. This creates a recombinant DNA molecule containing the erythropoietin gene.

3. Transformation: The recombinant DNA molecule is introduced into host cells (typically bacteria or yeast) using techniques like heat shock or electroporation. These host cells will serve as factories for producing erythropoietin.

4. Expression and production: The transformed host cells are cultured under controlled conditions to allow them to multiply and express the erythropoietin gene. This leads to the synthesis of large quantities of recombinant erythropoietin protein.

5. Purification: Once expressed, the recombinant erythropoietin protein needs to be purified from other cellular components and impurities present in the culture medium. Various purification techniques such as chromatography, filtration, and centrifugation are employed to obtain highly pure erythropoietin.

6. Formulation: The purified erythropoietin is then formulated into a suitable pharmaceutical product, often as a solution for injection.

B. Sherpas' extra abilities that can benefit the world if it was implemented

1. Expertise in high-altitude environments: Sherpas have extensive experience and knowledge about navigating and surviving in high-altitude regions, such as the Himalayas. This expertise can be invaluable in various fields, including mountaineering, scientific research, and even space exploration.

2. Cultural preservation and promotion: Sherpas have a rich cultural heritage that includes unique traditions, languages, and practices. Implementing their abilities can help preserve and promote this cultural diversity globally, fostering cross-cultural understanding and appreciation.

3. Sustainable tourism development: Sherpas' deep connection with their natural surroundings makes them excellent guides for sustainable tourism initiatives. Their knowledge of local ecosystems, conservation practices, and responsible trekking can contribute to the development of eco-friendly tourism models that minimize negative impacts on the environment.

4. Disaster management and rescue operations: Sherpas' resilience, physical endurance, and familiarity with treacherous terrains make them ideal candidates for disaster management teams. Their skills in search and rescue operations can save lives during natural disasters like earthquakes or avalanches.

5. Environmental advocacy: Given their close relationship with the Himalayan region's fragile ecosystem, Sherpas can play a crucial role in advocating for environmental protection measures. Their firsthand experiences of climate change impacts can raise awareness about the urgent need for sustainable practices globally.

6. Education initiatives: Implementing Sherpas' abilities in education initiatives can help bridge educational gaps in remote mountainous regions. They can serve as mentors or educators to empower local communities with knowledge about sustainable agriculture techniques, healthcare practices, or vocational skills.

7. Mental resilience training: The mental strength exhibited by Sherpas during challenging expeditions is remarkable. Implementing their abilities in mental resilience training programs can benefit individuals and organizations worldwide, helping them cope with stress, overcome obstacles, and achieve personal and professional goals.

8. Cultural tourism promotion: Sherpas' expertise in mountaineering and their rich cultural heritage can be leveraged to promote cultural tourism. By organizing cultural festivals, adventure sports events, or guided tours, Sherpas can attract tourists interested in experiencing their unique way of life while contributing to the local economy.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Fig. 1: The chemical structure of the erythropoietin that can benefit the project.

Research fields	Oriented percent	How?
gene therapy	40%	Using the study of genetics to benefit the medicine
Biochemistry	27%	Study of the proteins in this thesis
genetics	20%	Study of the Sherpas' genome
environmental study	13%	Study of the environmental conditions

Table 1: The data analysis of the research fields in this project

Percent of using research fields in this thesis

■ gene therapy ■ Biochemistry ■ genetics ■ environmental study

Fig. 2: Pie chart of the proportional percent among the used research fields

V. THE FIELD OF STUDY

The field of study of sherpas is primarily focused on understanding the unique physiology, culture, and mountaineering skills of the Sherpa people. Sherpas are an ethnic group native to the mountainous regions of Nepal, particularly in the Solu-Khumbu region of the Himalayas. Some key areas of study related to sherpas include:

1. **Anthropology:** Anthropologists study the cultural aspects of Sherpa society, including their traditions, beliefs, social structure, and religious practices. This field helps in understanding how Sherpas have adapted to living in high-altitude environments and their role as guides and climbers.

2. **Physiology:** Physiologists examine the physiological adaptations that allow sherpas to thrive at high altitudes. Sherpas have unique genetic traits that enable them to efficiently utilize oxygen and cope with low oxygen levels, making them highly skilled mountaineers.

3. **Mountaineering:** The field of mountaineering focuses on studying the technical skills and knowledge required for climbing mountains. Sherpas are renowned for their expertise in mountaineering and guiding climbers on treacherous terrains like Mount Everest. Research in this area may involve understanding their climbing techniques, equipment usage, rescue operations, and risk management strategies.

4. **Environmental Science:** Environmental scientists study the impact of human activities on mountain ecosystems and how these activities affect local communities like the Sherpas. This research helps in developing sustainable practices for tourism and mountaineering while preserving fragile mountain environments.

5. **Tourism Studies:** The growth of adventure tourism in Nepal has significantly impacted Sherpa communities economically and culturally. Researchers studying tourism focus on understanding its effects on local livelihoods, cultural heritage preservation, community development initiatives, and sustainable tourism practices.

VI. CONCLUSION

Sherpas are a group of people native to the mountainous regions of Nepal and Tibet, particularly known for their exceptional mountaineering skills and ability to thrive in high-altitude environments. The science behind Sherpas' abilities can be attributed to a combination of genetic, physiological, and cultural factors.

The project is inspired from the Sherpas' extra abilities by synthesizing more erythropoietin, which provide like-vaccine to benefit the blood patients. The purpose is benefiting the research fields and medicine aspect.

APPENDIX (CONS)

For further knowledge, look at the ethical points in this thesis "utilize Sherpas as research materials."

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